

Paper 9

GENDER EQUALITY-A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO WORKING WOMENS IN MANGALORE THALUK

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Abstract

Earlier women are deprived of economic resources and are dependent on men for their living. Women work often confined to domestic space, she had to do all household works, which are not recognised and unpaid. In the modern era, many women are coming out to work but they have to bear the dual responsibility. She is considered last and first to be shot because she is perceived as less competitive than her counterpart. Her general status in the family and society has been unrecognised.

Women's participation in India's workforce was extremely low compared to other countries in the world. The representation of women in India's workforce is below 28%. According to the 2017 World Economic Forum (WEF) Global Gender Gap Study, which ranks countries on gender criteria in health, education, economics and politics, India ranked 108 out of 144 countries on economic participation and opportunity.

This study is undertaken to know whether there is equality between men and women at the workplace and to what extent gender equality is effective at the workplace.

Keywords: Gender Equality, Workplace, Facilities, Gender Disparity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Earlier women are deprived of economic resources and are dependent on men for their living. Women work often confined to domestic space, she had to do all household works, which are not recognised and unpaid. In the modern era, many women are coming out to work but they have to bear the dual responsibility. She is considered last and first to be shot because she is perceived as less competitive than her counterpart. Her general status in the family and in the society has been unrecognised.

2. GENDER EQUALITY

Gender is defined as distinct from sex because it refers to the structure of society and culture. Which based on the biological sex of the person, defines his or her role in society; thus gender-based violence which is inflicted on a person because of their biological sex. A society in which there was no discrimination against anyone based on his or her sex could be

said to have achieved gender equality. Gender equality could be defined as full equality between the sexes.

“Just as a bird could not fly with one wing only, a nation would not march forward if the women are left behind”-Swami Vivekananda

Gender equality emphasizes that all human beings, be they men or women, are free to develop their abilities and make political and other assumptions without the limitations set by stereotypes, rigid gender roles. Their different aspiration should be valued equally and they would be treated equally to their respective needs. But law alone cannot do much. Sections of society have to work for their transformation and this is where NGOs, the media and people representative have to play a major role. Gender justice is genuine equality among human being where neither man is superior nor is a woman inferior. Gender equality is achieved when people can access and enjoy the same rewards, resources and opportunities regardless of whether they are women or men.

Several countries have made substantial progress in recent decades towards achieving gender equality in various aspects of society, especially in employment and education. All people have the right to work and the same opportunities for jobs. The business should be therefore striving towards the removal of barriers to the full and equal participation of men and women in the workforce. Employment opportunities based on their qualification and competency. Men and women have the right to have equal remuneration, benefit and treatment in respect of work of equal value. Equal opportunities when it has come to the promotion, job security, and all benefit and condition of services such as training and career advancement. They also have an equal right to protection of health and safe working condition, including reproductive health.

3. SCOPE

The study covers the information given by women worker in different sector. The scope of study is limited to only one taluk of Dakshina Kannada district. The study covers the position of women when gender equity at workplace is concerned.

4. OBJECTIVES

- To know whether there is equality between men and women at workplace.
- To understand the gender aware environment.
- To understand to what extent gender equality is effective at workplace.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The study undertaken includes both primary and secondary data. The primary data is firsthand information collected for the purpose of survey. The information for this study collected through questionnaire. The structured questionnaire was distributed to respondent in mangalore thaluk. The secondary data is obtained from various journals, books, magazines and a few websites. The data collected through questionnaire was put together in the form of tables and analysis, simple percentage method is used for the analysis.

6. DATE ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION**TABLE1: CHANCE OF GETTING JOB**

Considerations	No. Of Respondents	Percentage
Equal Chance	2	2
Not Equal Chance	46	46
Sometimes	52	52
TOTAL	100	100

N=100

Sources: Survey Data

Out of 100 respondents 2% were believe that there is equal chance of getting job. But 46% felt that there is no equal chance of getting job and remaining 52% felt that sometimes there are equal chances of getting jobs.

TABLE 2: SELECTION PROCESS

Selection	No of respondents	Percentage
Same	12	12
Different	49	49
Sometimes	39	39
TOTAL	100	100

N=100

Sources: Survey Data

Out of hundred respondents 12 % agreed that there is same selection process, 49% were agreed selection process is not same and remaining 39 % felt that it's sometimes same and sometimes different.

TABLE 3: METHOD OF TRAINING

Method	No of respondents	Percentage
Same	5	5
Different	50	50
Sometimes	45	45
TOTAL	100	100

N=100

Sources: Survey Data

Out of 100 respondents 5% agreed that there is same method of training is provided. 50% of them have agreed that it's different. And 45 % agreed there differs from organisation to organisation.

TABLE 4: POSSIBLITY OF CLIMBING THE LADDER OF HIRARCHY FOR MEN ABOVE WOMEN

Possibility	No of respondents	Percentage
Agreed	84	84
Not agreed	5	5
Sometimes	11	11
TOTAL	100	100

N=100

Sources: Survey Data

Out of 100 respondents majority were beliebed that Men are given more chance to climb the ladder of hierarchy, 5% not agreed with the above subject and remaining 11 % felt some time it happens with both.

TABLE 5: TREATMENT AT WORK PLACE

TREATMENT	No of respondents	Percentage
Equal	36	36
Not equal	64	64
TOTAL	100	100

N=100

Sources: Survey Data

Out of 100 respondents, majority felt that men and women are not equally treated at their work place and remaining 36% were believed that they were equally treated.

TABLE 6: PAYMENT

PAYMENT	No of respondents	Percentage
Equal	45	45
Not equal	55	55
TOTAL	100	100

N=100

Sources: Survey Data

Out of 100 respondents 55% of them replied that they are paid less compared to men and remaining 45% of them agreed that they will get equal payment compared to men.

TABLE 7: BIAS AT WORKPLACE

Bias	No of respondents	Percentage
Exist	70	70
Do not exist	30	30
TOTAL	100	100

N=100

Sources: Survey Data

Out of 100 respondents 70% were responded that there is existence of BIAS in workplace. Where as 30% said there is absence of Bias.

Table 8: JOB SECURITY

Job security	No of respondents	Percentage
Equal	90	90
Not equal	10	10
TOTAL	100	100

N=100

Sources: Survey Data

The study reveals that majority of respondents have equal job security compared to men and remaining 10 percent of respondents there is no job security for them.

TABLE 9: LEAVE AND RETIREMENT BENEFIT

	No of respondents	Percentage
Available	90	90
Not available	10	10
TOTAL	100	100

N=100

Sources: Survey Data

Out of 100 respondents majority of them said that they will get leave and retirement benefit. Remaining felt there is no benefit available.

7. FINDINGS

- Very little respondents believed that there is equal chance of getting job.
- Majority of respondents agreed that men are given more chance to climb the ladder of hierarchy.
- Very little respondents felt that they will get equal treatment at their workplace compared to men.
- The respondents replied according to their position at their workplace.

8. SUGGESTIONS

- All private employers should provide all facilities which are available for government employees.
- Working time for women evening must be less, they should be left early to home.
- There should be fair treatment in terms of all the aspects.
- Payment should be made as per their performance.
- Equal opportunities should be provided at workplace to show their talent and efficiency in their work.
- There should not be gender bias at workplace.

9. CONCLUSION

Gender inequality is one of the major issues faced by women in today's workplace particularly in private sector jobs i.e unorganised sector jobs. In government jobs women can fight for their right and gender equality laws in force. If the women are not paid properly, they have right to question and government cannot refuse to make the payment. So, in government jobs women were protected because of gender equality laws and regulations but in private sector women are exploited through gender bias particularly at unorganised sector. Especially the poor women who work there do not aware of their own rights. Private sector has to come up with different laws in order to avoid gender inequality. By this way we can achieve gender equality at our workplace.